

MECHANICAL AND TRIBOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF SiC WHISKER/
SILICON NITRIDE COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

The mechanical, thermal, electrical and tribological characteristics of SiC whisker/silicon nitride composite were studied.

Silicon nitride powder which contains densification aids of Y_2O_3 and La_2O_3 was mixed with silicon carbide whiskers and then hot-pressed at a temperature of 1800°C.

The Vickers hardness number increases and indentation fracture strength decreases as the content of SiC whiskers increases.

Thermal and electrical conductivities increase as the content of SiC whiskers becomes higher. Silicon carbide whiskers are not dispersed isotropically, but are oriented to the direction which is perpendicular to the pressure of hot-press sintering. Therefore, both conductivities have anisotropic characteristics. Conductivities perpendicular to the pressure of hot-press sintering are higher than those in the parallel direction.

SiC whiskers have an evident effect to reduce the wear rate. Wear properties of the composite ceramics are also anisotropic.

INTRODUCTION

Ceramic materials such as silicon carbide, silicon nitride, aluminum oxide, and zirconium oxide have been seriously considered as mechanical components. Each of them has its own superiorities and insuperiorities in the realms of mechanical, thermal, corrosive, electrical and tribological properties. It is sometimes quite difficult to

improve these properties in monolithic ceramics, at the same time.

Attempts which improve various mechanical properties of both metals and polymers by making composite materials have been undertaken quite intensively. Therefore, it is quite reasonable to try to make composite ceramics [1-4] which can be used as mechanical components such as bearings and gears. These materials should satisfy various demands which are high wear resistance, low friction, high fracture toughness, and high strength.

Although silicon carbide has superiorities in both friction and wear characteristics, it has a low fracture toughness. On the other hand, hot-pressed silicon nitride has a higher fracture toughness but lower characteristics in both friction and wear properties. Therefore we may expect a new material which has an acceptable fracture strength along with high tribological abilities when combining these two ceramics. Not only these mechanical and tribological properties, but thermal and electrical properties of silicon nitride will also be changed by the mixing.

The purpose of this paper is to provide a general view of the mechanical, thermal, electrical, and tribological properties of hot-pressed silicon nitrides which contain SiC whiskers.

Silicon nitride powder which contains densification aids of Y_2O_3 and La_2O_3 is mixed with silicon carbide whiskers (10, 20, 30 and 40 wt%) and then hot pressed at a temperature of $1800^\circ C$ and at a pressure of $4 \times 10^7 Pa$.

The effects of SiC whiskers on the hardness, fracture strength, thermal conductivity, electric conductivity, wear rate and the coefficient of friction of silicon nitride composites are examined experimentally.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES AND INSTRUMENTS

Hardness values of silicon carbide composites were obtained by Vickers hardness tester at the indentation load of 1N.

Thermal conductivities K , were calculated by

$$K = \alpha \cdot C \cdot d$$

where α , C , and d are diffusivity of heat, specific heat, and density, respectively. Diffusivity of heat and specific heat were measured by Laser Flash method.

Indentation experiments were carried out using the instrument shown schematically in figure 1. A steel ball was installed on a flat composite specimen. The diameter of the ball was 6.35 mm. A cantilever mechanism loads the ball at the speed of 200 N/min. The Hertzian contact between

Figure 1. Schematic representation of indentation fracture apparatus

Figure 2. Schematic representation of friction and wear apparatus

the ball and the flat specimen generates tensile stress around the contacting circle on both surfaces. The stress will introduce Hertzian cracks in the flat specimen. The occurrences of cracks were detected with an acoustic emission (AE) detector which was installed on a flat specimen holder.

Friction and wear experiments were carried out with a ring on block type instrument which is shown schematically in figure 2. Load was applied with a dead weight and sliding speed was varied from 50 to 600 mm/sec. An electric micrometer was set on the top of the block holder and the decrease of height of the block holder due to the wear of both block and ring specimens was measured by the micrometer. From these measurements the wear volume of the block specimen was calculated ignoring the wear of the ring specimen. The error due to this was less than 5% of the total wear volume of the block specimen. The friction force between the block and ring specimens was measured with a torque meter. The wear instrument was

housed in a plastic box to control atmosphere of which humidity is $50 \pm 5\%$ RH.

MATERIALS AND SINTERING PROCESS

Materials

The SiC whiskers made by Tokai Carbon LTD, had an average diameter of $0.5 \mu\text{m}$ and length was from 50 to $100 \mu\text{m}$. The whiskers were β -silicon carbide. The tensile strength of the whiskers was 3-14 GPa and the modulus of longitudinal elasticity was 400-700 GPa.

The silicon nitride matrix used was Hermann C. Starck's H1. The average particle diameter was $0.7 \mu\text{m}$. More than 97% of the powder was α -Si₃N₄. Densification aids were 7.5mol% Y₂O₃ and 7.5mol% La₂O₃ for most of the silicon nitride composites except for the composite which contained 40 wt% SiC. The latter material needed higher amounts of densification aids, they were 10 mol% Y₂O₃ and 10 mol% La₂O₃.

Sintering processes

Silicon carbide whiskers were dispersed by a mechanical stirring for one hour in water and passed through a #350 mesh sieve to remove the large clusters of whiskers which were difficult to disperse.

Before the silicon nitride matrix was mixed with the whiskers, the densification aids were added and the matrix was ball milled for twenty-four hours in ethanol. After being dispersed for ten minutes in water by ultrasonic waves, 10, 20, 30 and 40 wt% whiskers were added and the mixture was dispersed for another ten minutes by a mechanical stirring. Then the mixture was filtered and preformed into 20X40X1mm thin slabs.

Hot-press sintering was carried out using a graphite mold and a heater of high frequency inductive heating. A stack of about fifteen of the preformed slabs were pressed with the pressure of $4 \times 10^7 \text{ Pa}$ in the mold for 60 minutes at the temperature of 1800°C.

The hot-pressed composite ceramics were then ground with a #200 diamond whirl.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of SiC whiskers on hardness

Effect of SiC whiskers on hardness values is shown in figure 3. The hardness value increases as the content of SiC whiskers increases. The increase of hardness value will be attributed to the dispersed SiC whiskers which prevent the slides of silicon nitride particles at grain boundary.

Relative density of silicon nitride composite decreases as the

Figure 3. Effect of SiC whiskers on hardness number

Figure 4. Weibull's plots for indentation fracture
 Maximum load : 2.2 KN
 Radius of ball : 3.18 mm
 Relative humidity : 50 ± 5 %RH

content of SiC whiskers increases [5]. In the cases of monolithic silicon nitride or silicon carbide, ceramics of lower density, have lower hardness values [6]. However, our composite ceramics showed a quite opposite tendency and the composite silicon nitride of lower density had a higher hardness value.

Indentation experiments

Ueno and Toibana examined [7] three points bending strength of silicon nitride composite and found that the content of silicon carbide whiskers had little influence on the average value of bending strength at room temperature. Besides these bulk properties, local strength of the composite should be considered for the application to tribological components such as rolling bearings. In these applications, fracture will be restricted around contacting points on the surface and the strength in the restricted area should be different from the strength of bulk material. Indentation fracture strength was then measured by using the AE detector to examine the local strength of composite silicon nitrides.

Figure 4 shows the effect of the content of SiC whiskers on the cumulative distribution of the occurrence of acoustic emissions which are generated by the extension of cracks during indentation. These results

present that the average strength and Weibull modulus increase for the indentation fracture as the content of whiskers decreases.

Ueno and Toibana showed the opposite tendency of Weibull modulus of the strength of bulk material[7]. That is, Weibull modulus of the failure of three points bending decreases as the content of SiC whiskers increased. This means that SiC whiskers improves the reliability of the composite ceramics. The mixing procedures introduce many blocks of undispersed SiC whiskers and these blocks might have worked as defects. In the case of three points bending, the distribution of these defects can be considered as uniform and this uniformity makes the Weibull modulus of the bulk material larger. But, in the case of local stress fields such as indentation experiments, the distribution cannot be considered as uniform and this inhomogenic distribution decreases the Weibull modulus. Experimental results for a monolithic silicon nitride are not shown in the figure 4, because no fracture could be detected within the load range of the experiment (the maximum load was 2.2 KN).

The above results suggest that the SiC whiskers improve the reliability of the bulk mechanical properties but they degrade the strength against local pressures.

Thermal and electrical properties of the composite ceramics

Figure 5 shows the effect of SiC whiskers on thermal conductivity of Silicon nitride composites at room temperature. The thermal conductivity of the composite silicon nitrides increases as the content of SiC whiskers increases. The thermal conductivity in the direction perpendicular to the pressure of hot-press sintering is higher than those in the parallel direction.

Similar tendencies can be seen for the electric conductivity of the composite silicon nitrides. Figure 6 shows the effect of the content of SiC whiskers on the electric resistance of silicon nitride composites. The electric resistance decreases as the content of SiC whiskers increases. The low electric resistance enhances the capability of the silicon nitride composites to be machined with an electrospark machine [8]. The resistance in the direction perpendicular to the hot-press pressure is lower than those in the parallel direction.

The anisotropic characteristics of both thermal and electrical conductivities mean that SiC whiskers do not disperse uniformly but they are oriented to the direction perpendicular to the pressure of hot-press sintering. The expected situation of SiC whiskers is shown schematically

in the figure 6.

Figure 5. Effect of SiC whiskers on thermal conductivity

Figure 6. Effect of SiC whiskers on electric resistance

Friction and wear characteristics

Wear experiments were carried out with the composite ceramics which contained various amounts of silicon carbide whiskers sliding against a silicon carbide ring. Figure 7 shows the relationship between the

Figure 7. Effect of SiC whiskers on wear rate
 Ring specimen : SiC
 Sliding speed : 200 rpm
 Load : 5 N
 Relative humidity : 50±5 %RH

content of SiC whiskers and wear rate of two kinds of composite silicon nitride surfaces. One is surface "A" which is perpendicular to the hot-press pressure and the other is the surface "B" which parallel to the pressure. The wear rate of monolithic silicon carbide is shown at the right hand corner of the figure. The densification aid of the monolithic silicon carbide was 2 wt% Al_2O_3 . The hot-press pressure and its temperature were 30 MPa and 2100°C, respectively.

The strict comparison of the wear rate between the composite silicon nitride and the monolithic silicon carbide has no meaning, because their sintering conditions were not the same. However, we may conclude that silicon carbide, as a basic property, has better anti-wear property than silicon nitride and the mixing of silicon carbide whiskers to silicon nitride improve considerably the wear characteristics of silicon nitride.

The reduction of wear rate for the surface "A" is more evident than that for the surface "B". The directionality of wear characteristics is attributed to the anisotropic dispersion of silicon carbide whiskers which has been presented in the experiments of the thermal and electrical conductivity (figures 5 and 6). The sliding surface "A" has higher surface density of silicon carbide whiskers than that in the surface "B", and this reduces the wear rate of the composite ceramics more effectively.

Figure 8. Effect of SiC whiskers on coefficient of friction content of whiskers
 a : 0 wt%
 b : 10 wt%
 c : 30 wt%

Ring specimen : SiC
 Load : 5 N
 Relative humidity : 50 ± 5 %RH

Figure 8 shows the relationship between coefficients of friction and sliding speeds as a function of the content of SiC whiskers. Both the sliding speed and the content of whiskers give no evident effect on the coefficient of friction. These results are quite reasonable because there is little difference between the coefficient of friction of a monolithic silicon carbide and that of a monolithic silicon nitride.

CONCLUSION

Mechanical and tribological properties of SiC-Whisker-Composite silicon nitride were examined and the following conclusions are drawn from the experimental results.

- (1) As the content of SiC whiskers increases, the hardness value of the composite increases.
- (2) The larger the content of SiC whiskers becomes, the higher the thermal and electrical conductivity. These conductivities in the direction parallel to the hot-press pressure are lower than those perpendicular to

the pressure.

(3) As the content of SiC whiskers increases, indentation fracture strength becomes lower.

(4) Wear rate of the composite ceramics decreases as the content of SiC whiskers increases.

(5) Wear rate of the composite ceramics for the surface perpendicular to the pressure of hot-press sintering is lower than that for the surface parallel to the pressure.

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